

Beyond Borders: Unpacking the Dreams of Nepali Students Planning to Study in Australia

A Research Paper

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Submitted by:

Sali Dewan, PhD Scholar

salidewan04@gmail.com

Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences

Pokhara University

Nepal

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Researcher's Declaration of Originality

I hereby declare that the independent study report entitled “**Beyond Borders: Unpacking the Dreams of Nepali Students Planning to Study in Australia**” submitted to the **11th LSME International Research Conference, on “Re-Visioning Practice in Education, Healthcare and Business amidst Global Challenges”** to be hosted from 12th to 13th November 2024, online by London School of Management Education is original. This research report has been submitted to the peer review team of the conference.

Sali Dewan

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ABSTRACT

The central theme of this study is to explore the dreams and aspirations of Nepali students planning to study in Australia, with a specific focus on the contextual dynamics of Pokhara. This research is highly relevant to the conference theme of "Re-Visioning Practice in Education, Health Care, and Business Amidst Global Challenges" as it delves into the educational aspirations that are shaped by global trends and local socio-economic conditions.

For this study, Pokhara was selected using purposive sampling, acknowledging the significant presence of approximately 35 abroad study consultancies in the area. Out of these, 7 consultancies were purposively selected. The student sample size was determined through convenience sampling, culminating in a total of 202 respondents. Primary data were collected using structured questionnaires through direct interviews with students from 10 consultancies. To achieve the study's objectives, both descriptive and inferential statistical analyses were employed.

The findings reveal that most students are teenagers, unmarried, and from low-income families. Most respondents have secondary-level education, predominantly in the management stream, and half had received a B grade in their current education status. The majority completed their education in private institutions.

Gender-based differences emerged, with male respondents predominantly having completed secondary education, while female respondents were more likely to have completed bachelor's degrees, master's degrees, or other qualifications such as nursing. The primary source of information about studying abroad was family members. Most respondents relied on their own judgment or advice for making decisions about studying in Australia.

Key motivational factors for studying in Australia included academic quality, personal growth, career opportunities, and financial considerations. The study highlighted that career and life opportunities, improvement in English language skills, and a good academic experience are significant expectations influencing the decision to study in Australia. Societal influence factors were determined by sex and age, while family income influenced career opportunities. Moreover, personal growth and financial consideration factors showed significant relationships with

educational status. The stream and GPA of current education were significantly related to career growth and academic quality.

Finally, the study identified that visa and immigration processes are major challenges for students deciding to study in Australia. These insights contribute to the broader discourse on educational practices amidst global challenges, aligning with the conference's focus on re-visioning practices in education.

Keywords: Educational Aspirations, Globalized Education, Nepali Students, Studying Abroad.

Introduction

Students' mobility is a global phenomenon, and Nepal is not an exception (Tamang & Shrestha 2021). However, an alarming trend of Nepali students' foreign migration in the last few years has posed serious concerns for society and academia. Ghimire's study (2023) highlighted that the count of Nepali students pursuing higher education overseas, encompassing diploma and language courses, demonstrates a consistent annual rise. Ghimire (2023) reported for the University World News that 82000 Nepali students had obtained No Objection Certificate (NOC)s in the first nine months of the fiscal year 2022-23 when as many as 114, 000 students had acquired NOCs in the fiscal year 2021-22 and in the last 13 years the number was 416,364. The number was increased by 12.74 percent (MOEST, 2022).

Student's migration seeks growing attention in both origin and destination countries. The destination countries gain income on the one hand, and on the other hand, student's countries of origin loss their intellectual wealth (Jong & Fonseca, 2020) due to the increasing trend of student migrations.

Nepal, a country nestled in the Himalayas, has witnessed a growing trend of students pursuing higher education abroad, with Australia emerging as a popular destination (Shrestha & Dhakal, 2019). The decision to study abroad is influenced by various factors, including academic opportunities, career prospects, cultural exposure, familial expectations, and financial considerations. Nepal's education system faces challenges such as limited access to quality higher education institutions, inadequate infrastructure, and political instability (Bista & Pandey, 2018).

This study seeks to explore the dreams of Nepali students planning to study in Australia, aiming to shed light on the multifaceted factors driving their educational choices. By examining their aspirations, expectations, and perceived challenges, we aim to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on international student mobility and cross-cultural education.

1.2 Statement of the Problems

With an unstable economy, uncertain future, and lack of employment opportunities, many Nepali youths are trying to go abroad during their college years with the expectation of permanently settling down there (Joshi, 2022). Nepali students have long been attracted to foreign countries for their improved facilities, higher standard of living and increased exposure (Tamang & Shrestha, 2021).

Australia, renowned for its high-quality education system, diverse cultural landscape, and favorable post-study work opportunities, has emerged as a popular destination for Nepali students seeking to fulfill their academic and career aspirations (Australian Government, 2021).

Research Questions

- What is the socio economic and demographic background of students pursuing study in Australia?
- What is the educational status of students for decision to study in Australia?
- What are the major motivational factors that influence on decision to study in Australia?
- What is the major expectation of students for decision to study in Australia?
- Is there any significant relationship between social and educational status with motivational factors and expectational factors?

Research Objectives

The general objective of the study is to explore the dreams and aspirations of Nepali students planning to study in Australia. The specific objectives are:

- To identify the current educational status, education stream, CGPA and type of educational institutions of emigrant students in Pokhara
- To assess the perception of emigrant students on motivational factors for decision to study in Australia
- To analyze the relationship between motivational factors and expectation with socio-economic variables.

Significance of the Study

This study explores Nepali students' aspirations to study in Australia, providing insights into motivations driving international student mobility. It informs the development of tailored support services, broader education sectoral policy, and international relations, contributing to academic literature on cross-cultural education and international student mobility.

Limitation of the Study

This study explores Nepali students' aspirations in seven educational consultancies, focusing on social capital theory and expectation value theory. Data was collected between January and July 2024 in Pokhara, with 202 respondents selected using a convenient sampling method. The study's limitations impact its generalizability and applicability to broader contexts. The study's findings are based on a quantitative method and structured and semi-structured questionnaire tools.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework: Social Capital Theory

Social capital is a broad term that encompasses the 'norms and networks facilitating collective actions for mutual benefits of the individuals in the society globally. As the social capital theory states, people's decision to migrate is mainly influenced by interpersonal ties that bring the migrants, former migrants and non-migrants in origin and destination countries through ties of kinship, friendship and shared community origin (Massey et al, 1993).

Theoretical Framework: Expectancy-Value Theory

Expectancy-value theory, proposed by Eccles and Wigfield (2002), suggests that individuals' choices and behaviors are influenced by their expectations of success and the perceived value of the outcomes associated with those choices. Expectancy for success and subjective task value are two direct predictors of achievement choice.

Eccles and Wigfield (2002) further proposed four types of value: intrinsic value (the inner enjoyment a person gains from performing the task), attainment value (the importance of success in undertaking a specific task), utility value (the usefulness of achieving a goal or completing a task) and cost. Cost also has four sub-components: task effort cost (how much time and effort are put into the task), outside effort cost (how much time and effort are spent on tasks other than the task of interest), loss of valued alternatives (LOVA, the loss of other options due to conducting the

task), and emotional cost (negative emotions such as stress, worry and anxiety caused by engaging in the task) (Barron and Hulleman, 2014).

Besides, Eccles emphasized EVT as a task-specific motivational model (Wigfield et al., 2016) because individuals may have completely distinct perceptions of expectancy, values and cost for different tasks. In the context of this study, expectancy-value theory provides insights into the motivational factors driving Nepali students' aspirations for studying in Australia, including expectations of academic success, career opportunities, and personal growth (Smith & Johnson, 2018).

Empirical Review

Nepal, a nation nestled between China and India, has witnessed significant changes in its education sector in recent years. The study also found that academic reputation, career opportunities, and quality of life influence Nepali students' study abroad decisions (Shrestha, 2018). Nghia's (2019) study among Vietnamese students further identified family, teaching and learning practices, and cultural issues in the home and host countries as factors which motivate students to seek education internationally. Tuxen and Robertson (2019) found students to be motivated by migration and job opportunities in the host country.

The study further reported that significantly fewer jobs are available in Nepal compared to the country's graduates. Thus, some students perceive the better living and working conditions outside

Conceptual Framework

Student decision to study in Australia is influenced by motivational factors, expectation, family income, occupation, and education background. Emigration decisions are dependent on socio-demographic, economic, motivational, and expectation factors.

Independent variables

Dependent variable

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the study

Research Methodology

Study Design

The study utilized a cross-sectional survey in Pokhara to explore Nepali students' aspirations to study in Australia, employing a descriptive and inferential research design.

Study Area

The study setting was Pokhara Metropolitan City where most of the higher educational institutions are concentrated. The target population of the study was students who prepared the IELTS, PTE, GRE, Duolingo, etc. from the selected consultancies in Pokhara.

Population and Sample Size

In Pokhara, there are 35 abroad study consultancies working in student visa for Australia, UK, USA, Canada, etc. registered in Pokhara Metropolitan Office, out of which 202 students studying in IELTS and PTE out of 820 were selected based on pilot survey results

Data Collections Tools:

Data was collected through convenience sampling, semi-structured questionnaires, and face-to-face interviews from respondents preparing IELTS and PTE in educational consultancies in Pokhara, ensuring privacy and confidentiality.

Data analysis and Management

Two hundred two students' data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, using manual and computer programs. Data was presented using frequency analysis, cross-tabulation, Chi-square tests, and ANNOVA tests.

Ethical Considerations

In alignment with the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), the study

acknowledges the importance of stakeholder engagement, transparency, and societal relevance. Although the study employed a survey method, future research should incorporate focus groups and interviews to ensure deeper participation and insight from Nepali youth.

The study followed ethical guidelines, obtained informed consent, protected confidentiality and privacy, and allowed participants to withdraw at any time without consequences.

Reliability and Validity

The study identified variables and designed a questionnaire, pre-tested with 22 students in Pokhara, ensuring reliability and consistency. All 202 feedback were complete, with Cronbach's alpha values above 0.70.

Results And Discussion

Social and Demographic profile

Table 1.1

Frequency analysis of socio-demographic profile of the respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Age (years) Min=17 Max=31 Mean=19.73 S.D.=3.060	15-19 years	140	69.3
	20-24 years	38	18.8
	25 years and above	24	11.9
Sex	Male	115	56.9
	Female	87	43.1
Caste/ethnicity	Brahmin/Chhetri	129	63.9
	Janajati	45	22.3
	Dalits	18	8.9
	Others	10	5.0
Marital Status	Unmarried	187	92.6

	Married	15	7.4
Family Types	Nuclear	158	78.2
	Joint	44	21.8

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Majority of respondents (69.3%) were aged 15-19 years, with an average age of 19.73. Most were male (56.1%) and female (43.1%), with 63.9% belonging to Brahmin/Chhetri, followed by Janajati (22.3%), Dalits (8.9%), and others (5.0%). Most were unmarried (92.6%) and 78.2% from nuclear or joint families.

Economic Status of Family

Table 1.2

Analysis of economic status of respondent's family

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Family occupation	Agriculture	27	13.4
	Business	67	33.2
	Government Job	32	15.8
	Private Job	26	12.9
	Others	50	24.8
Family Income Mean=176718.92, SD=525626.657	Below Rs. 100000	57	28.2
	Rs.100000-500000	139	68.8
	Above Rs.500000	6	3.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The majority of the respondents' families work in business, followed by government, agriculture, and private jobs. Over two-thirds earn between Rs.100000-500000 per month, with 28.2% below and 3.0% above.

Educational status of the Respondents

Table 1.3

Frequency distribution educational status of the respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Current education status	+2	150	74.3
	Bachelors	34	16.8
	Master	3	1.5
	Others	15	7.4
Stream of current Education	Science	60	29.7
	Management	114	56.4
	Others	28	13.9
GPA of current Education	C	7	3.5
	C+	32	15.8
	B	103	51.0
	B+	53	26.2
	A	7	3.5
Type of school/college completed current education	Government-funded	60	29.7
	Community Funded	17	8.4
	Private	125	61.9

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The majority of the respondents (74.3%) have completed secondary education, with 16.8% having a bachelor's degree, 1.5% having a master's degree, and 7.4% having a master's degree. Management is the most frequently passed stream, followed by science. Over half have achieved B grade, and most have completed their education from private, government, or community institutions.

Study planning in Australia

Table 1.5

Respondents' perception on study planning in Australia

Variables	opinion	Frequency	Percent
Relative or family members live in Australia	Yes	115	56.9
	No	87	43.1
Course of study in Australia	IT	32	15.8
	Engineering	18	9.0
	Management	95	47.0
	Arts	10	5.0
	Nursing	22	10.8
	Science	25	12.4
Knowledge received from study abroad programme (N=273) <i>(multiple choice questionnaire)</i>	Teacher/Professor	26	12.9
	Family members	80	39.6
	Relatives	41	20.3
	Peer Groups/Friends	56	27.7
	Newspapers	10	5.0
	Electronic media	49	24.3
	Others	11	5.4

Advised to go abroad for higher studies (N=235) <i>(multiple choice questionnaire)</i>	Family	66	32.8
	Self	141	70.1
	Professor/Teacher	6	3.0
	Peers' groups	14	7.0
	Relatives	8	4.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The table shows that most respondents (56.9%) have relatives or family members in Australia, and most plan to study management, followed by information technology, science, nursing, engineering, and arts. 39.6% have gained reliable knowledge from family, peers, electronic media, teachers, others, and newspapers.

Descriptive Analysis of motivational Factors

Motivational factors have been measured using 5-point Likert Scale composed of altogether 5 statements with the scales ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree where, Scale: 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

Table 1.6

Descriptive statistics of the motivational dimensions composite scores

Factors	Mean	Standard Deviation
Academic Quality	4.23	0.62
Personal growth	4.03	0.66
Career opportunities	4.16	0.72
Financial Consideration	3.55	0.77
Societal influence	4.07	0.99

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Academic quality dimension has the highest score with mean value 4.23 followed by career opportunities with a score 4.16. According to the finding the least important perception has financial consideration with a score of 3.55.

Rank analysis of expectation on study in Australia

Table 1.7

Rank analysis of expectation on study in Australia

Statement	RII	Rank
Avoid the unacceptable political and social conditions	0.75	8
Immigrate in the future	0.65	10
More freedom and be independent	0.80	6
Gain international and cross-cultural perspectives	0.79	7
Good academic experience	0.90	3
Increase the level of my English language skills	0.92	2
Expand career and life opportunities	0.93	1
Get to know people from other countries	0.82	5
Gain other life skills	0.86	4
Influences from friends with study abroad experience	0.67	9

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The surveyed participants ranked expand career and life opportunities as the most important expectation factor that decide the youth to study in Australia with a relative important index of 0.93. And the immigrate in the future with RII of 0.65. This factor scored the ten ranks.

Independent Sample t-test motivational and expectational factors across Gender

Independent sample t-test has been applied to find out the significant difference between the impact factors of motivational factors on study in Australia (academic quality, personal growth, career opportunities, financial consideration and societal influence) across gender.

Table 1.8**Motivational Factors across Gender**

Factors	Gender	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	p-value
Academic Quality	Male	16.85	2.52	.932	.336
	Female	17.04	2.48		
Personal growth	Male	16.02	2.78	1.316	.253
	Female	16.24	2.47		
Career opportunities	Male	16.57	2.79	.009	.926
	Female	16.80	2.98		
Financial Consideration	Male	14.30	3.19	.924	.338
	Female	14.06	2.90		
Social Influence	Male	16.48	3.35	6.680	.010
	Female	15.98	4.64		
Expectation from abroad study	Male	40.06	4.88	-1.329	.185
	Female	40.97	4.80		

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The study found no significant relationship between sex and academic quality, personal growth, career opportunities, financial consideration, societal influence, or expectation and gender, with p-values greater than 0.05, indicating a significant relationship between sex and these factors.

Analysis motivational factors across demographic variables

One way ANOVA test has been applied to find out the significant difference between demographic variables and motivational factors of study in Australia.

Table 1.9**Motivational actors of studying Australia across demographic variables**

Variables		AQ	PG	CO	FC	SI
Age	F-value	0.381	0.084	0.314	0.795	4.775
	Sig value	0.684	0.191	0.731	0.453	0.009
Family	F-value	0.268	1.083	0.654	0.367	1.077
Occupation	Sig value	0.898	0.366	0.625	0.832	0.369
Family Income	F-value	0.257	1.138	3.291	0.579	0.541
	Sig value	0.773	0.323	0.039	0.561	0.583
Education status	F-value	0.279	3.764	0.405	2.832	0.367
	Sig value	0.841	0.012	0.750	0.040	0.777
Stream	F-value	0.473	0.392	3.697	0.677	0.376
	Sig value	0.624	0.676	0.027	0.509	0.687
GPA	F-value	2.344	1.404	2.673	0.916	1.850
	Sig value	0.046	0.234	0.033	0.455	0.121

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Note: AQ= Academic Quality, PG=Personal Growth, CO= Career Opportunities, FC= Financial Consideration and SI= Societal Influence

The study reveals age significantly influences societal influence, while motivational factors are not. Family occupation and income impact career opportunities. Educational status affects personal growth and financial consideration, while academic quality and CGPA are related. No significant association exists between gender and expectation.

Challenges of affecting decision to study in Australia

Table 4.11**Distribution of challenges of affecting decision to study in Australia**

Challenges	Frequency	percent
Financial constraints	117	67.2
Visa and immigration processes	126	72.4
Academic prerequisites	81	46.6
Family opposition	28	16.1
Lack of information	55	31.6
Others	22	12.6
Total	429	246.6

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Based on the multiple responses' questionnaire, more than seven out of ten (72.4%) mentioned that visa and immigration processes is affecting the decision-making process of study in Australia.

Summary of major findings

The study reveals that 74.3% of Nepali students have completed secondary education, with a majority passing through management. Most have achieved B grade, with 61.9% completing their education from a private institution. Most students are male and completed their education from community-funded institutions. Social-cultural theory is used to understand how cultural norms, societal expectations, and familial influences influence Nepali students' aspirations for studying abroad. Seven in ten students follow their own conscience for studying in Australia, with academic quality, personal growth, career opportunities, and financial consideration being important factors. Expanding career and life opportunities, increased English language skills, and good academic experience are the most important expectations. Societal influence has a significant relationship with sex and gender, while age, family occupation, family income, current education status, and CGPA are not associated with expectations.

Conclusion

The study reveals that most students are teenagers, unmarried, and from average-income families. They have completed secondary education with a management stream and have completed their education from private institutions. Family members often provide information about studying abroad, but students also consider academic quality, personal growth, career opportunities, and financial considerations. Factors such as societal influence, family income, and education status also influence these decisions. Visa and immigration processes are a significant challenge.

Implications

Based on the study's findings, the following suggestions and recommendation for the government, education institution and stakeholders are made:

- Nepal's Government needs to reform education policy, program and system.
- Enhance promotional efforts highlighting academic excellence, career pathways, and cultural integration programs to attract and retain Nepali students.
- Streamline visa processes, expand scholarship opportunities, and develop support mechanisms that address financial concerns and cultural adaptation challenges.
- Strengthen pre-departure orientation programs, integrate cross-cultural training, and establish peer support networks to enhance students' preparedness and overall satisfaction.

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